

FINAL REPORT

Laboratory bioassay to determine the attractiveness of traps against bed bugs *Cimex hemipterus*

Guideline(s)
n/a

Study Director
Dr. Jan Šklíba

Report Issue Date
10. 09. 2025

Test Facility
i2L Research Europe s.r.o.
Lipová 1789/9
České Budějovice 370 05
Czech Republic

Sponsor
InnoC SRL
18, Rue Joseph Desmet
1332 Genval
Belgium

Study Monitor
Anne-Catherine Mailleux

Study Numbers
i2L Study Code: 25/141

COMPLIANCE STATEMENT

The undersigned Study Director hereby declares that the work described in this report was performed under their supervision and that the report provides a true and accurate reflection of the methods used and the results obtained.

Dr Jan Šklíba
Study Director

10.09.2025

Date

Dr Pavel Foltan
Facility Management

10.9.2025

Date

All raw data and signed final report will be archived at i2L Research Europe s.r.o. for a period of ten years. At the end of this period, all data relating to this report will either be retained by i2L Research Europe s.r.o. for a further disclosed period at an extra cost, destroyed at the Sponsor's consent or passed on to the Sponsor at the Sponsor's expense.

Report circulated to:	Study Monitor	1 e-copy
	Study File	1 original
	Study Director	1 e-copy

Study Code: 25/141

STUDY INFORMATION

Laboratory bioassay to determine the attractiveness of traps against bed bugs, *Cimex hemipterus*

Testing facility	i2L Research Europe s.r.o. Lipová 1789/9 370 05 České Budějovice Czech Republic
Sponsor	InnoC SRL 18, Rue Joseph Desmet 1332 Genval Belgium
Study Monitor	Anne-Catherine Mailleux acmailleux@domobios.com
Study Director	Dr Jan Šklíba jskliba@i2lresearch.com
Study start date	21. 07. 2025
Experimental start date	18. 08. 2025
Experimental end date	20. 08. 2025
Study end date	10. 09. 2025

Test item:

Name	Active substance	Lot/Batch Number	Physical description	Storage conditions	Expiry date	i2L Research code
Domobios bed bugs footboard traps also called universal trap Nidoan	n/a	n/a	2-element plastic traps with sticky circles	ambient room temperature <i>(i2L default)</i>	30.07.2027 <i>(i2L default)</i>	25073002

Reference item:

Name	Active substance	Lot/Batch Number	Physical description	Storage conditions	Expiry date	i2L Research code
Bed bug blocker	n/a	n/a	Black plastic furniture leg saucers	ambient room temperature <i>(i2L default)</i>	30.07.2027 <i>(i2L default)</i>	25073001

CONTENTS

Study Information.....	3
Contents.....	5
Summary	6
1. Introduction	6
1.1. Study purpose	6
1.2. Trial location.....	6
2. Methods.....	6
2.1. Test systems	6
2.2. Test item and reference item.....	6
2.3. Test arenas	7
2.4. Experimental design	7
2.5. Test conditions.....	8
2.6. Data collected.....	8
2.7. Statistical analyses	9
3. Results	9
4. Conclusions	10
5. References	11
Appendix I: Raw data.....	12
Appendix II: Climatic conditions.....	13

SUMMARY

A laboratory bioassay was required to assess the efficiency of a trap against bed bugs, *Cimex hemipterus*, with a comparison with a competitor product. In each replicate out of four, 30 adults were released into a test arena containing both trap types. Captures were recorded after 24, 40, and 48 hours. The Domobios/Nidoan traps captured more than 65 % of bed bugs within 24 hours and over 80 % after 48 hours. In contrast, the Bloker traps caught only a single individual (< 1 %).

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Study purpose

The purpose of this laboratory bioassay was to evaluate the effectiveness of a bed bug trap, using *Cimex hemipterus* as the test system, and to compare its performance with that of a competitor trap.

1.2. Trial location

The study was conducted at i2L Research Europe s.r.o in České Budějovice, Czech Republic.

2. METHODS

2.1. Test systems

Bed bugs (*Cimex hemipterus*) were sourced from a laboratory colony maintained at the Czech University of Life Sciences, Prague (originally collected in Dar es Salaam, Tanzania). Mixed-age adult individuals of both sexes were used, with a sex ratio close to 1:1. Last blood meal was provided to them 14 days before the test initiation.

2.2. Test item and reference item

Domobios Bed Bug Footboard Traps (also called Nidoan) were provided by the Sponsor, together with a competitor product, the Bed Bug Blocker. Both trap types were used according to the instructions provided on their respective packaging.

2.3. Test arenas

The study was conducted in transparent boxes measuring 0.6 m × 0.4 m × 0.3 m, each fitted with a ventilated lid containing a large mesh window. A 2-cm wide Fluon® (liquid PTFE) barrier was applied around the inner walls to prevent insect escape. The floor was lined with filter paper, secured along its edges with paper tape.

2.4. Experimental design

Four replicates were conducted, each represented by a single test arena (box) containing both types of traps (Fig 1a,b). The trial started an hour before the lights were turned off for the night, to simulate the behaviour of the bed bugs during the night when they are looking for a host. 30 bed bugs were released in the center of each test arena. The 2 different traps were placed near opposite corners of the arena. The binary choice design was selected because, in the literature, dual-choice assays are considered a robust method to evaluate insect preferences by directly comparing two stimuli under identical conditions (Harraca et al., 2012; Singh et al., 2015b; Weeks et al., 2011). In the center of the traps, a plastic container filled with a mixture of 50 g yeast, 100 g sugar, and 400 ml of warm water (35 °C) was placed on an inverted 100 mL plastic cup. The mixture mimicked the CO₂ emissions by a human host (Singh et al., 2015a). After 16 hours, the yeast mixture was removed, and the number of bed bugs remaining outside the traps was recorded. Since multiple bedbugs were found hiding beneath some of the traps at this occasion, this possibility was prevented by adding weights (plastic cups with sand) on the top of these traps. At 24 h, the number of bed bugs inside the traps were counted. Further assessments were conducted at 40 and 48 h. To avoid positional bias, the placement of traps was rotated between arenas.

Fig. 1. Experimental setting: a) traps with the sugar– yeast mixture containers installed, b) closed experimental boxes, c) counting bedbugs stuck in a Domobios/Nidoan trap.

2.5. Test conditions

The temperature of 27 ± 2 °C, relative humidity 70 ± 10 % and photoperiod of 12L:12D was maintained during the test. No significant violations of these conditions were detected (Appendix II).

2.6. Data collected

At 16 h, only the numbers of bedbugs outside traps were recorded. At the following assessments (at 24, 40 and 48 h) the records contained:

- 1) number of bedbugs inside Domobios/Nidoan traps that were stuck on the sticky circle (Fig 1c)
- 2) number of bedbugs inside Domobios/Nidoan traps that walked freely inside the traps
- 3) number of bedbugs inside Bloker traps
- 4) number of bedbugs outside traps

2.7. Statistical analyses

Mean percentage of individuals (out of 30 per replicate) located in the four categories mentioned above (2.6.) was calculated for each assessment timing. Numbers of bedbugs trapped in the respective trap types were compared using paired t-test performed with Minitab 21.2 (2022).

3. RESULTS

The Domobios/Nidoan traps captured over 65 % bedbugs at 24h and over 80 % of them after 48 h (excluding individuals freely walking on the traps without being stuck). The competitor Bloker traps captured only one bedbug (< 1%, Table 1, Fig. 2). The difference between traps in terms of the number of captured bedbugs was highly significant (paired t-test, $n = 4$, $p < 0.01$) at any assessment interval. The raw data are presented in Appendix I.

Table 1. Mean \pm SD % of bedbugs found at different locations at various time intervals

Hours after test initiation	0	16	24	40	48
Inside Domobios/Nidoan - stuck	0	-	65.8 \pm 11	73.3 \pm 7.2	80.8 \pm 5.7
Inside Domobios/Nidoan - not stuck	0	-	13.3 \pm 6.1	13.3 \pm 7.2	11.7 \pm 4.3
Inside Bloker	0	-	0.8 \pm 1.7	0.8 \pm 1.7	0.8 \pm 1.7
Outside traps*	100	40.8 \pm 31.2	20 \pm 7.2	12.5 \pm 5	6.7 \pm 4.7

* including bedbugs that managed to hide beneath the traps. This was prevented after 16 h

Fig. 2. Mean \pm SD % of bedbugs trapped by Domobios/Nidoan traps (being stuck on sticky circles) and Bloker traps at various time intervals after the test initiation.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The Domobios traps (universal trap Nidoan) captured more than 65 % of bed bugs released to test arenas within 24 hours and over 80 % after 48 hours. In contrast, the Bloker traps (Interceptor) caught only a single individual (< 1 %).

The Domobios/Nidoan universal traps were proven to have a high efficiency in trapping bedbugs *Cimex hemipterus*. In contrast, almost no bedbugs were trapped by the competitor Bloker traps.

5. REFERENCES

Harraca, V., Ryne, C., Birgersson, G., & Ignell, R. (2012). Smelling your way to food: can bed bugs use our odour? *Journal of Experimental Biology*, 215(4), 623–629.

Minitab 21.2 (2022) MINITAB, available at: <http://www.minitab.com/en-US/products/minitab/>.

Singh, N., Wang, C., & Cooper, R. (2015a). Effectiveness of a sugar–yeast monitor and a chemical lure for detecting bed bugs. *Journal of economic entomology*, 108(3), 1298–1303.

Singh, N., Wang, C., & Cooper, R. (2015b). Potential of various bed bug interceptors and monitors to detect *Cimex lectularius* and *Cimex hemipterus* in apartments. *Journal of Economic Entomology*, 108(6), 2780–2786.

Weeks, E. N. I., Logan, J. G., Birkett, M. A., & Pickett, J. A. (2011). A review of the biology and control of bed bugs. *Pest Management Science*, 67(10), 1105–1117.

APPENDIX I: RAW DATA

Numbers of bedbugs outside and inside the traps at various assessment intervals:

Replicate	Hours after test initiation	0	16	24	40	48
1	Inside Domobios - stuck	0	-	19	21	25
	Inside Domobios - not stuck	0	-	5	4	5
	Inside Bloker	0	-	0	0	0
	Outside traps*	30	6	6	5	0
2	Inside Domobios - stuck	0	-	16	20	22
	Inside Domobios - not stuck	0	-	6	7	4
	Inside Bloker	0	-	1	1	1
	Outside traps*	30	23	7	2	3
3	Inside Domobios - stuck	0	-	24	25	26
	Inside Domobios - not stuck	0	-	3	2	2
	Inside Bloker	0	-	0	0	0
	Outside traps*	30	3	3	3	2
4	Inside Domobios - stuck	0	-	20	22	24
	Inside Domobios - not stuck	0	-	2	3	3
	Inside Bloker	0	-	0	0	0
	Outside traps	30	17	8	5	3
Mean %	Inside Domobios - stuck	0	-	65.8	73.3	80.8
	Inside Domobios - not stuck	0	-	13.3	13.3	11.7
	Inside Bloker	0	-	0.8	0.8	0.8
	Outside traps*	100	40.8	20.0	12.5	6.7

* including bedbugs that managed to hide beneath the traps. This was prevented after 16 h.

APPENDIX II: CLIMATIC CONDITIONS

No violation of the conditions required was detected.